
Research Article

Nutrient Intake and Nitrogen Balance of West African Dwarf (WAD) Goats fed Cassava Peel Meal Supplemented with Varying Levels of African Yambean Concentrate

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Abstract

A total of eight (8) intact West African Dwarf (WAD) bucks with a mean live weight range of 18.85 - 19.94 kg and aged between 18 and 24 months was used in a 4 × 4 Latin square experiment to determine the intake and nitrogen balance of the cassava peel meal based - diets supplemented with African Yambean Meal (AYBM) in diets T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ with levels of 0, 10, 20 and 30% respectively. The respective dietary treatments were assigned to individual animals in metabolism cages. Weekly body weight values were recorded, feed and dry matter intake measured and nitrogen balance study conducted. Results showed that the Dry matter intake (DMI) (g/d) values were 608.52, 572.32, 548.60 and 552.93 for diets T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ respectively. The values were statistically similar (P>0.05). The values generally indicated that the animals on various dietary treatments showed positive DMI status. The metabolic faecal nitrogen (MFN) (g/100gDM), endogenous urinary nitrogen (EUN) (g/day/kg W^{0.75}) and digestible crude protein (DCP) (g/kg W^{0.75}) values were 0.17, 0.19, 0.22, 0.25; 0.24, 0.03, 0.02, 0.03 and 0.44, 0.56, 0.81, 1.81 respectively for diets T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄. All the diets promoted a positive nitrogen balance between the treatment groups. The relationship between urinary nitrogen (g/day/Wkg^{0.75}) and absorbed nitrogen (g/day/Wkg^{0.75}) was significantly (P<0.05) correlated between the control diet T₁ and diet T₃ with values of 0.91

and 0.82 respectively. The correlation coefficient, however showed some remarkable improvement from 0.49 to 0.64 for diets T₂ and T₄ respectively. While both parameters were positively correlated within the AYBM diets, the coefficient of correlation was only significant (P<0.05) for diet T₃ (30% AYBM). Energy digestibility coefficients were 43.04, 50.37, 53.35 and 53.30% respectively for WAD bucks fed diets T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄. The values differed (P<0.05) significantly among the various dietary treatments. The study concludes that AYBM meal in cassava peel based diets improved nutrient digestibility, nitrogen intake and ensured a positive nitrogen balance, thereby boosting the maintenance requirements of WAD bucks. Therefore, farmers can supplement cassava peel meal based diets with African Yambean meal up to 30% without fear of compromising digestibility of nutrients.

Key words: Nitrogen balance, nutrient retention, African yam bean, WAD bucks

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Introduction

The current focus in the livestock industry within the sub - Saharan region is feed sufficiency that will enhance production. Livestock is the world's fastest growing agricultural sub - sector that accounts for about 40% of agricultural Gross Domestic Product (GDP) globally (Richkowsky *et al.*, 2016). While providing livelihood for millions of resource - poor farmers, feed sufficiency, whether from conventional or non - conventional sources; the common goal is to get the best out of the existing or available resources for optimum animal performance. In Nigeria, increasing population pressure (about 200 million) has led to most cropped area being extended to land hitherto considered unsuitable for this purpose. Thus, feeding ruminants becomes a challenge as the poorly developed grazing reserves and related infrastructure are put to other uses, resulting in frequent forage shortage and degradation of the natural rangeland which threatens the sustainability of this farming system. Goats are a very important animal resource to the people of sub-Saharan Africa. These animals are known to improve livelihoods of smallholder farmers across the region but the challenge has often been feed availability. However, food and feed production will

have to compete for land and water resources in the prevailing variability of climate change environments.

Cassava is an important annual root crop grown widely by tropical and sub-tropical farmers. It is an important part of the diet of more than 800 million people in Africa. It is the highest supplier of carbohydrates among staple crops and ranks fourth among food crops in developing countries after maize, rice and wheat (FAO, 1991). Cassava has often been associated with the rural poor, yet it has the potential to transform economies (Reeve, 2017). Increasing the productivity of Cassava through the utilization of its peels will improve the livelihood of most resource-poor livestock farmers. Cassava peels are produced in large quantities in Southern Nigeria, from the processing of cassava for human consumption to industrial and export purposes. Unfortunately, this enormous feed resource has received very little attention and more than 50 million tonnes of peels is often discarded as waste annually. Cassava peel is rich in metabolizable energy (3.03 Mcal/Kg DM) but low in nitrogen (Smith *et al.*, 1988). Generally fibrous crop residues are poor sources of fermentable nitrogen, as their crude protein is below the level required by rumen microorganisms. Also, these crop residues are also low in easily degraded carbohydrates, minerals and other nutrients required to balance the products of digestion to requirements (Anya, 2018). All these result in limited intake, poor rumen function, increased methane emission and low animal productivity.

The use of African yambean (*Sphenostylis stenocarpa*), an under-exploited and often classified minor grain legume that is cheap and readily available protein source in cassava peel meal based diets is a strategy that intends to overcome the nutritional constraints of using cassava peels, it will close the feed deficit gap, reduce feed cost and sufficiently tackle seasonal fluctuations in forage quality and quantity. This would on the long run encourage increases in flock sizes, provide insurance against external shocks as well as increase the productivity of goats.

In sub-Saharan African, dry season feeding of ruminants has always been a constant challenge to farmers, particularly the smallholders and their livelihoods as feed supplies are limited. Most crop residues are the major contributors to livestock diets during this critical period. However, poor feed utilization and seasonal fluctuations in feed availability and quality are contributory factors that lead to less-than-optimal productivity of animals on these diets (Lukuyu *et al.*, 2016). Overall livestock productivity and efficiency is largely determined by feed intake, excellent digestibility, adequate utilization and maintenance of physiological balance or homeostasis.

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Livestock farmers therefore need all the information to identify available feed resources and diversify sources of nutrients that would enhance nutritional efficiency of the animal.

This study was therefore carried out to investigate the utilization cassava peel meal (CPM) based diets supplemented with varying levels of African yambean concentrate fed to WAD bucks in the humid zone of Nigeria.

Materials and methods

Location of study

The experiment was carried out in the Ruminant Unit of the Teaching and Research Farm, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike - Abia State, Nigeria. Umudike is situated within the tropical rainforest zone and witnesses an annual rainfall of about 2177mm in 148 -155 rain days. Its relative humidity is over 72% during the rainy season with an average ambient temperature of 25.5°C within a range of 22 - 32°C (Okereke, 2008).

Processing of cassava peel and African yambean seed meal

Cassava peels of TMS 30555 variety were collected fresh from the Department of Crop Science commercial "Garri" processing unit of the University of Calabar, Calabar. The peels were from 10-12 months old plants. The peels were properly sun dried for a period of 3-6 days during which they were regularly turned to give even drying to a moisture content of 10%. The peels could sometimes have tuber linings as a result of the method of removing the peels. The sun-dried cassava peels were then milled into 2mm sieve size with the hammer mill and used in the study as dried cassava peel meal (CPM). African yambean (*Sphenostylis stenocarpa*) seeds (Nsukka brown variety) were purchased from local famers in Obudu and Obanliku Local Government Areas in the Northern parts of Cross River State. The undecorticated brown seeds were boiled for 30 minutes following the method of Ukachukwu and Obioha (2000) for *Mucuna* seeds. Water was made to boil at 100°C in a large (mammoth) cooking pot before the seeds were poured in. The seeds were allowed to boil for 30 minutes. Water was decanted using local baskets and the seeds sun-dried on aluminum roofing sheets for 3 days before being milled and used as yambean seed meal (AYBM) to compound the experimental diets.

Experimental diets

Four experimental diets designated T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ were formulated as presented in Table 1. Diet T₁ served as the control and contained no African yambean (AYBM) seed meal. Diets T₂, T₃, and T₄, contained 10, 20, and 30% of AYBM respectively. The diets were allotted randomly to the four animal groups. Each animal within a group was offered 1kg of an assigned concentrate diet daily for 90 days. The concentrate diets were fed at 0800 hour daily. Clean drinking water was provided *ad-libitum* for each animal within the period. Each animal was provided with a salt lick block.

Proximate analyses of experimental diets

All the experimental diets including CPM and African yambean seed meal AYBSM were analyzed for proximate composition using AOAC (2000) methods (Table 2).

Table 1: Gross Composition of Experimental diets

Ingredients (%)	Diets			
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄
Cassava peel	46.00	46.00	46.00	46.00
African yambean seed meal	-	10.00	20.00	30.00
Wheat offal	33.00	23.00	13.00	3.00
Palm kernel cake	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00
Bone meal	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Salt	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Table 2: Proximate composition of experimental diets, cassava peel meal (CPM) and African yambean seed meal (AYBM)

Parameter (% DM)	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	CPM	AYBM
Dry matter	89.44	89.35	89.42	89.62	90.10	88.50
Crude protein	10.56	10.96	11.36	11.44	3.22	22.10
Crude fibre	12.47	11.05	10.31	10.11	14.73	5.92
Ether extract	4.50	4.61	4.80	4.94	0.91	7.53
N-free extract	51.38	53.61	54.33	54.62	65.67	47.67
Ash	10.35	9.12	8.62	8.49	5.57	5.28
Gross energy (kcal/g)*	3.45	3.42	3.31	3.28	3.60	5.23

*Calculated

Each determined value was obtained from triplicate samples per treatment

Management of experimental animals

A total of eight (8) intact WAD bucks averaging 19.39 ± 0.36 kg (range 18.85 - 19.94 kg) in weight and aged 1 - 1 1/2 years were used to determine the digestibility of nutrients in diets used in this study following a 4 x 4 Latin square design experiment that was replicated twice (4 buckseach). The animals were selected from the goat herd of the Teaching and Research farm. The animals were first dewormed and purged of external parasites using thiabendazole and pfizone respectively. The animals were previously zero-grazed and supplementary feeding of 0.4 - 0.5 kg concentrates offered per head per day. The bucks were subsequently housed in previously disinfected individual metabolism cages measuring 1.0 x 0.8 x 0.6 m and offered the experimental diets in 4 phases.

Before the first phase, a preliminary period of 7-day feeding was done to get the animals conditioned to the cage environment. Each period lasted for 21 days and each buck received 1 kg of one of 4 experimental diets for 14 days. The animals had access to clean drinking water throughout the experimental period. Daily voluntary feed intake was measured and recorded. Total faeces and urine voided were collected during the last 7 days (14 - 21). This was usually, done in the morning before feeding and watering. Each buck was offered each of the remaining 3 experimental diets in rotational periods of 21 days each. The last 7 days in each of the feeding phases, was also used for total urine and faecal collection. Samples of the diets (T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄) were analysed for dry matter and other chemical composition.

The faeces were weighed fresh, dried and bulked for each animal. A sub-sample from each was dried in a forced-draft oven at 100 - 105°C for 48 hours and used for dry matter (DM) determination. Another sample was dried at 60°C for 72 hours for determination of proximate components. Total urine for each animal was collected daily in the morning before feeding and watering. Urine was collected in a graduated transparent plastic container placed under each cage to which 10 ml of 25% H₂SO₄ was added daily to reduce volatilization of ammonia (NH₃) from the urine. Ten percent (10%) of the daily outputs of urine by each animal were kept in plastic bottles, numbered and stored in a deep freezer at -5°C. The samples were collated for each animal, bulked and sub-samples taken for analyses at the end of every 7 days collection period.

Analytical procedure

All feed and faecal samples were analysed for proximate components using AOAC (2000) methods. Nitrogen in urine samples was also determined by AOAC (2000) methods.

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Statistical analysis

The data generated from the nutrient digestibility study were pooled since the experiment was replicated twice and all data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) as applicable to a 4 x 4 Latin square design using SPSS 15.0 (2006) statistical package. Mean differences between treatments were separated using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Duncan, 1955) as outlined by Obi (1991).

Results and Discussion

The dry matter (DM), nutrient intake and N-balance of WAD goats (bucks) fed the experimental diets are presented in Table 3. The DM intake (g/d) values were 608.52, 572.32, 548.60 and 552.93 for diets T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ respectively. The values were similar (P>0.05). Diet T₁ recorded the highest DMI which was followed by T₂, T₄ and the least was T₃. DM in the control diet (T₁) was the highest consumed probably due to the fact that it contained the lowest crude protein content (Table 2). The low, though non-significant DM intake of the bucks fed the various dietary treatments in this study agrees with the findings of Swanson *et al.* (2000) who reported no difference in DM intake when ruminants fed low quality forages were supplemented with protein. The marginal differences among dietary treatments may also have been responsible for the non - significant increase in DM intake even as dietary nitrogen levels increased from diets T₁ to T₄. Increasing levels of AYBM in the test diets (T₂ - T₄), apart from improving the nitrogen levels, could also have made the rations increasingly palatable, but this was not the case in this study. The presence of tannins in AYBM and the inclusion of palm kernel cake in the ration might have impacted some bitter taste as the level of AYBM increased in the rations. Also AYBM is known to cause flatulence (excessive accumulation of gases in the stomach) which invariably discourages feed intake (Janardhanan *et al.*, 2003; Azeke *et al.*, 2005). The low, though non-significant DMI of bucks fed diet T₃ and T₄ however agrees with the assertion that low nitrogen contents may have significantly reduce the DMI of such feeds (Sauvant *et al.*, 1991; Ukpabi, 2007).

DMI expressed as percentage of body weight was 3.16 for the control diet and 2.87; 2.91 and 2.84 for diets T₂, T₃ and T₄ respectively. Though the value for the control diet was higher than that of the test diets (T₂, T₃ and T₄), there was no significant (P>0.05) differences among them. The values generally indicated that the animals on various dietary treatments showed positive DM status. The values reported in this study seem low but falls within the range of 2.8 -3.0% recommended for meat type goats in the tropics (Devendra and Mcleroy, 1982; Akinsoyinu, 1985; Ahamefule, 2005; Ukpabi,

2007). Also the values obtained in this study falls within the range of 2.5- 4.0% recommended for indigenous goats of Nigeria (Nuru, 1985).

Table 3: Dry matter and N-balance of WAD goats fed the experimental diets

Parameter	Diets				SEM
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	
Mean live weight (kg)	19.26	19.94	18.85	19.50	0.36
Mean live weight (Wkg ^{0.75})	9.19 ^{ab}	9.44	9.05 ^b	9.28 ^{ab}	0.11
DMI (g/d)	608.52	572.32	548.60	552.93	46.77
DMI (g/d/Wkg ^{0.75})	66.14	62.02	64.11	60.04	6.59
DMI as %BW	3.16	2.87	2.91	2.84	0.29
CP-intake (g/d)	63.78	62.72	60.00	62.40	5.34
N - Intake (g/d)	10.29	10.04	9.97	10.02	0.84
N - Faeces (g/d)	5.37	5.91	5.55	5.76	0.89
N - Urine (g/d)	2.82	3.17	3.38	3.26	0.58
N - Absorbed (g/d)	4.92	5.38	5.92	5.96	0.40
N - Balanced (g/d)	2.11	2.09	2.30	2.47	0.59
N - Absorbed (g/wkg ^{0.75})	0.54	0.63	0.66	0.63	0.04
N - Balance (g/wkg ^{0.75})	0.23	0.22	0.29	0.27	0.07
N - Intake (g/wkg ^{0.75})	1.12	1.09	1.11	1.10	0.10
Apparent N digestibility (%)	47.63 ^b	53.04 ^{ab}	59.27 ^a	55.83 ^{ab}	3.25

^{a,b}Means on the same row with different superscripts differ significantly (P<0.05)

Nitrogen (N) intake values (g/d) were 10.29, 10.04, 9.97 and 10.02 for diets T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ respectively. Though, N - intake in diet T₃ was the least, there were no significant differences (P>0.05) among the treatments. The least N-intake recorded for diet T₃ followed by T₄ further buttress the fact that DMI is positively correlated with N-intake (Sauvant *et al*, 1991; Ukpabi, 2007). Nitrogen output in faeces (g/d) followed a similar trend as N-intake. There were no significant differences (P>0.05) among the dietary treatments. However, AYBM diets had higher faecal-N value than the control. It has been reported that faecal-N increases as the N-intake increases (Ibeawuchi *et al*, 1993; Matenga *et al.*, 2003; Ukpabi, 2007). Nitrogen output in urine (g/d) followed a similar pattern to that of nitrogen in faeces. Animals on diet T₃ had the highest value (3.38) followed by T₄ (3.26), T₂ (3.17) and T₁ (2.83) respectively. The values recorded for the AYBM diets (T₂ – T₄) were consistently higher than that of the control (diet T₁), but these values did not however, show any significant difference (P>0.05). The trend observed in this study showed that faecal and urinary nitrogen increased with nitrogen ingestion

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(McDonald *et al.*, 1995; Matenga *et al.*, 2003; Ahamefule, 2005). Also, the non-significant faecal and urinary-N values observed among dietary treatments is in agreement with the reports of Preston (1986) and Ahamefule (2005) who had observed that faecal and urinary nitrogen was not significantly affected by nitrogen intake and any difference observed among animals on the different dietary treatments may be attributed to variation in nitrogen metabolism. Animals on diet A consumed more DM and more nitrogen and should excrete more nitrogen in its urine ideally. The deamination process in the rumen may have probably resulted in the production of more ammonia from the AYBM diets as opposed to the control. Hadjipanayiotou *et al.* (1991) reported that diets of high crude protein content result in high concentration of rumen ammonia - NH_3 , which rumen microorganisms may not efficiently utilize, and ammonia is excreted through the urine. The low and non-significant ($P>0.05$) values of N in urine obtained in this study showed that rumen microorganisms efficiently utilized the CP in the control diet (diet T₁) and other diets containing AYBM.

The values of N - absorbed (g/d) were 4.92, 5.38, 5.92 and 5.96 for diets T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ while the N-balance (g/d) values were 2.11, 2.09, 2.30 and 2.47 respectively for diets T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄. There were no significant ($P>0.05$) differences among the various values obtained for both parameters. The N-balance followed a similar trend as ingested N. All the animals were in positive N-balance, which indicated that their maintenance requirements were satisfied by the various diets. If the N-balance is considered in relation to N- intake, it may be observed that N-intake improved with the inclusion of AYBM. The values obtained for N-absorbed and N-balance in this study were however lower than those reported by Ahamefule (2005) with pigeon pea seed meal (PSM) and Ukpabi (2007) with mucuna seed meal (MSM). This observation could be due to the fact that the AYBM used in this study still contained some residual anti-nutrient even after boiling that may have affected N-absorbed and N-balance. In line with this observation, Matenga *et al.* (2003) advocated proper processing of legume seed meals before feeding to goats to improve N-intake and retention.

The relationship between faecal nitrogen (g/kg DM) and N-intake (g/d) is presented in Table 4. The correlation coefficients (r) were 0.80, 0.48, 0.99 and 0.97 respectively for diets T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄. Except for diet T₂, the AYBM based diets (T₃ and T₄) had higher correlation coefficients than the control. All values except that of diet T₂ were however statistically significant ($P<0.05$). The intercept on the ordinate axis (Table 4) shows the N-excreted in the faeces for each of the diets when N-intake was hypothetically zero, which is the metabolic faecal N (MFN). The values (g/100gDM) were 0.17, 0.19, 0.22

and 0.25 respectively. The mean value of 0.21 ± 0.03 g/100gDM obtained for WAD goats fed AYBM diets in this study compared favourably with the value of 0.24gN/100g DM often quoted for ruminants (Ahamefule, 2005) but lower than 0.43gN/100g DM reported by Akinsoyinu (1974) for WAD goats. Brun-Bellut *et al.* (1991) reported that very small estimates of endogenous losses of nitrogen in faeces may be obtained if rumen degradable protein (RDP) was not sufficient for microbial synthesis in which case endogenous-N which reached the rumen would be utilized. Thus, the portion of faecal microbial protein, which comes from endogenous-N, would not be accounted for in MFN. It is also possible that the low values for MFN obtained in this study may have resulted from the method used in processing the AYBM (i.e. boiling) which probably left some residual tannin and other anti-nutrients in the AYBM (Ezueh, 1984; Hernandez - Infante *et al.*, 1998; Klu *et al.*, 2001; Azeke *et al.*, 2005). Also this low value according to Ahamefule (2005) could also be due to variations within breed as well as the type of feed (nutrition), management factors, environmental conditions and the effect of season in which this study was carried out.

The relationship between urinary nitrogen (g/day/Wkg^{0.75}) and absorbed nitrogen (g/day/Wkg^{0.75}) is presented in Table 5. In this study, both parameters were poorly but significantly ($P < 0.05$) correlated in the control diet T₁ and diet T₃ with values of 0.91 and 0.82 respectively. The correlation coefficient however showed some remarkable improvement from 0.49 to 0.64 for diets T₂ and T₄ respectively. While both parameters were positively correlated within the AYBM diets, the coefficient of correlation was only significant ($P < 0.05$) for diet T₃. The intercept on the urinary-N axis gave the urinary- N at zero N absorption, which is endogenous urinary-N (EUN) in g/d/kgW^{0.75}. The EUN values were 0.024, 0.029, 0.020 and 0.031 respectively for diets T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄. A mean EUN of 0.03 ± 0.004 was obtained for WAD goats on the AYBM diets in this study which was however lower; than the value of 0.06 g/day/Wkg^{0.73} reported by Akinsoyinu (1974) for WAD goats. The control (diet T₁) had a seemingly high EUN value (0.024 g/day/Wkg^{0.75}) compared to the AYBM diets. This variation in the value of EUN observed within breed may be due to urea recycling in the rumen peculiar to ruminants (Akinsoyinu, 1974; Ahamefule, 2005; Ukpabi, 2007).

Nitrogen balance (g/day/KgW^{0.75}) was linearly correlated with Absorbed-N (g/day/Kg W^{0.75}) in all diets except in diet B, where it was non-significant ($r = 0.36$; $P > 0.05$) as presented in Table 6. The Absorbed-N at zero N-balance multiplied by 6.25 gave the digestible crude protein (DCP) requirement for maintenance while the gradient of lines relating N-balance to Absorbed-N gave the indices of biological value (Mba *et al.*, 1975;

Ahamefule, 2005; Ukpabi, 2007). The value of 0.81g DCP/kg/W^{0.75} for goats on diet T₃ in this study compares favourably with 0.76 - 0.88gDCP/KgW^{0.75} recommended by ARC (1980). The value of 1.81gDCP/kgW^{0.75} obtained for diet T₄ in this study is higher than the range reported by ARC (1980). On the other hand, the value of 0.56gDCP/kgW^{0.75} obtained for diet T₂ in this study compares favourably with earlier values of 0.51g/kgW^{0.75} reported for WAD goats (Onwuka *et al.*,1985) while the value of 0.44gDCP/kgW^{0.75} obtained for diet (T₁) fell below this value. However, the mean biological value of 0.73 ± 0.12 obtained for diets containing AYBM-compares favourably with 0.83 obtained for goats on the control diet and indicates that the efficiency of the AYBM based diets were as good as the control. The dry matter and nutrient digestibility coefficients are presented in Table 7. Dry matter digestibility (DMD) coefficients (%) were 41.36, 47.58, 51.07 and 47.67 respectively for diets T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄. The values were significantly (P<0.05) different. The highest mean value obtained for bucks fed diet T₃ (51.07%) agrees with the reports of McDonald *et al.*(1995) that DMD decreases as DMI intake increases which depicts that DMD is negatively correlated with DMI (Table 3). The values for diets T₂ and T₄ did not strictly conform to the above report. However, the mean value of 48.77 ± 1.51% obtained for AYBM based diets is slightly higher than 41.36% obtained for diet T₁. This trend was reversed when mean DMI (551.95 g/day) for diets T₂, T₃ and T₄ was lower than.608.52g/d obtained for diet T₁ (Table 3). This also confirms the negative correlation that exists between DMD and DMI. Crude protein digestibility coefficient values were 47.61, 51.65, 59.28 and 55.69% for diets T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ respectively. There were significant differences (P<0.05) between the treatments but the results showed that all diets containing AYBM (10 - 30%) had better CP digestibility than diet T₁. Diet T₃ was outstanding and differed (P<0.05) from other treatments, while diets T₂ and T₄ were similar (P>0.05) to diet T₃ and not different from the control. However, it has also been reported that thermal processing of seed meals improves CP digestibility (McDonald *et al.*, 1995). Crude fibre digestibility coefficient values were 14.95, 21.78, 31.75 and 42.24% for diets T₁,T₂, T₃ and T₄ respectively. There were significant differences (P<0.05) among the diets. Results showed that diet T₄ had better CF digestibility when compared to other diets. Though diet T₂ and T₃ were similar (P>0.05), diet T₃ was also not different from diet T₄, while diet T₂ was also similar to the control. All AYBM based diets had better digestibility compared to the control. Diet T₁ which had the least CP digestibility also had the lowest CF digestibility. Though, variations exist among breeds including other factors such as type of feed and season, the relatively low values of CF digestibility obtained in this study suggest that the cellulolytic activities of rumen microorganisms may have been hindered particularly

among goats on diet T₁ (Crampton and Harris, 1969; Leng, 1993; McDonald *et al.*, 1995; Ukpabi, 2007).

Ether extract (EE) digestibility was highest for bucks on diet T₂ (89.46%), followed by those on diet T₃ (89.43%), T₄ (88.34%) and T₁ (82.97%) respectively. The AYBM based diets were similar ($P > 0.05$) but statistically different from the control. However, the mean value of $89.08\% \pm 0.01\%$ for bucks fed diets containing AYBM (10 - 30%) was higher than 82.97% obtained for the control. The EE digestibility obtained in this study was outstanding when compared to that of pigeon pea meal (Ahamefule, 2005) and mucuna seed meal (Ukpabi, 2007). This might be due to the fact that AYBM is actually rich in oils (Santos *et al.*, 1996; Oshodi *et al.*, 1997; Gruneberg *et al.*, 1999) and the level of EE in the respective dietary treatments were also high (Table 2). Ikhatua and Adu (1984) reported similar high EE digestibility coefficient for Red Sokoto goats fed forage and groundnut haulm supplemented with concentrate.

Table 4: Regression equation between faecal-N (g/kgDM (Y) and N-intake (g/day) (X) in WAD goats fed the experimental diets.

Diets	Regression equation	Correlation Coefficient (r)	SE	Intercept on Y-axis	MFN (g/100g)
T ₁	$Y = 1.09 - 0.68X$	0.80*	0.02	1.65	0.17
T ₂	$Y = 1.75 - 0.60X$	0.48	0.09	1.88	0.19
T ₃	$Y = 1.96 - 0.57X$	0.99*	0.12	2.21	0.22
T ₄	$Y = 1.25 - 0.47X$	0.97*	0.03	2.54	0.25

* = Significant ($P < 0.05$)

SE = Standard Error

MFN = Metabolic Faecal Nitrogen.

Table 5: Regression analysis and correlation coefficients between urinary nitrogen (g/day/Wkg^{0.75}) (Y) and absorbed nitrogen (g/day/Wkg^{0.75}) (X) in WAD goats fed the experimental diets.

Diets	Regression equation	Correlation Coefficient (r)	SE	Intercept on Y-axis	EUN (Wkg ^{0.75} /day)
T ₁	$Y = 4.38 - 12.06X$	0.91*	0.04	0.226	0.024
T ₂	$Y = 0.91 - 4.48X$	0.49	0.05	0.029	0.029
T ₃	$Y = 10.80 - 9.68X$	0.82*	0.06	0.019	0.020
T ₄	$Y = 10.05 - 7.53X$	0.64*	0.04	0.031	0.031

* = Significant ($P < 0.05$), SE = Standard Error

EUN = Endogenous Urinary Nitrogen

Table 6: Regression analysis and correlation coefficients between N-balance (g/day/Wkg^{0.75}) (Y) and N-absorbed (g/day/Wkg^{0.75}) (X) in WAD goats fed the experimental diets.

Diets	Regression equation	Correlation Coefficient (r)	SE	N-absorbed at zero N-balance	BV	DCP for maintenance (g/d/kgW ^{0.75})
T ₁	Y = 1.38 - 0.68X	0.76*	0.06	0.07	0.83	0.44
T ₂	Y = 0.04 - 0.910X	0.36	0.02	0.09	0.31	0.56
T ₃	Y = 1.11 - 1.942X	0.94*	0.06	0.13	0.91	0.81
T ₄	Y = 1.17 - 1.911X	0.90*	0.15	0.29	0.97	0.81

* = Significant (P< 0.05)

SE = Standard Error

DCP = Digestible Crude Protein

BV = Biological value

Table 7: Apparent digestibility coefficient (%) of nutrients in the experimental diets

Constituents	Diets				SEM
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	
Dry matter	41.36 ^b	47.58 ^{ab}	51.07 ^a	47.67 ^{ab}	2.62
Crude Protein	47.61 ^b	51.65 ^{ab}	59.28 ^a	55.69 ^{ab}	3.13
Crude Fibre	14.95 ^c	21.78 ^{bc}	31.75 ^{ab}	42.24 ^a	4.79
Ether Extract	82.97 ^b	89.46 ^a	89.43 ^a	88.34 ^a	1.25
N-Free Extract	39.55	46.42	49.01	48.37	3.23
Energy	43.04 ^b	50.37 ^{ab}	53.35 ^a	53.30 ^a	3.32

^{abc} Means on the same row with different superscripts differ significantly (P< 0.05).

Nitrogen free extract (NFE) digestibility values were 39.55, 46.42, 49.01 and 48.37% respectively for diets T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄. The values did not differ (P>0.05) significantly among treatment and did not reveal or show any definite pattern. The mean value of 47.93± 0.35% for diets containing AYBM was higher than 39.55% obtained for the control diet. This is an indication that NFE digestibility in AYBM diets was better when compared to the control. The NFE digestibility values obtained in this study were low when compared to that of pigeon pea meal (Ahamefule, 2005), mucuna seed meal (Ukpabi, 2007) and groundnut haulm supplemented with concentrates (Ikhatua and Adu, 1984). This might be probably due to the high oligosaccharide content of African yambean (Bergthaler *et al.*, 2001; Janardhanan *et al.*, 2003) coupled with the associative effect of other ingredients in the respective diets. Energy digestibility coefficients were

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43.04, 50.37, 53.35 and 53.30% respectively for bucks fed diets T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄. The values differed ($P < 0.05$) among the various dietary treatments. The mean value of $52.34 \pm 1.35\%$ obtained for diets containing AYBM is lower than 43.04% obtained for the control, diet T₁. The coefficient of digestibility increased from diets T₁- T₄ as the energy contents of the diets declined. Since animals eat to meet their energy need, induced intake would suggest that more of the less or low energy diets would be consumed. This trend was not reflected as shown by the DMI in this study (Table 3). However, since it is known that energy digestibility is negatively correlated with energy intake (McDonald *et al.*, 1995), then the non-significant energy digestibility coefficients of diets could find justification in this study, since energy intake were low for AYBM based diets but energy digestibility coefficients tend to be high compared to the control that hitherto recorded high energy intake (DMI) but lowest digestibility coefficient. Apparent N-digestibility (%) values were 47.63, 53.04, 59.27 and 55.83. Significant differences existed ($P < 0.05$) among the respective dietary treatments in this study. However, apparent N-digestibility presented a similar trend as in apparent CP digestibility (Table 7). The mean value for AYBM based diets was $56.05 \pm 0.31\%$ which is higher than 47.63% for diet T₁, which suggest that N supplied by boiled AYBM based - diets was better utilized than that of the control diet.

Conclusion and recommendation

The study concludes that African yambean meal (AYBM) in cassava peel based diets improved nitrogen intake and ensured positive nitrogen balance, thereby boosting the maintenance requirements of WAD bucks. Dry matter intake was positively correlated with Nitrogen balance. Faecal and urinary nitrogen increased with nitrogen ingestion with the intake of AYBM. Diets containing AYBM had improved biological value and were outstanding in terms of crude protein digestibility. It is therefore recommended that farmers can supplement cassava peel meal based diets with African yambean meal up to 30% without fear of compromising digestibility of nutrients in West African Dwarf goats (bucks).

References

Ahamefule, F.O. (2005). Evaluation of Pigeon pea - cassava based diets for goat production in South-eastern Nigeria. Ph.D. Thesis. College of Animal Science and Animal Production. Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike, Abia State-Nigeria.

Continental J. Agricultural Science

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ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Akinsoyinu, A.O. (1985). Nutrient requirements of sheep and goats in Nigeria. In: *Small Ruminant Production in Nigeria*. Adu, I.F, Taiwo, B.B.A. Osinowo, A.O and Alhassan W.S. (Eds). NAPRI, Shika-Zaria. Nigeria. Pp141-148.

Anya, M.I. (2018). Rumen degradation of cassava peel meal supplemented with graded levels of African Yambean by West African Dwarf sheep in the humid zone of Nigeria. *International Journal of Advances in Agricultural Science and Technology*, 5(8): 24-31.

AOAC (2000). Association of official Analytical chemists. Official methods of analysis 17th edition. Washington DC. USA.

ARC (1980). Agricultural Research Council. *The nutrient requirement of ruminant livestock*. Farnham Royal, Commonwealth Agricultural Bureaux.

Azeke, M.A., Fretzdoff, B., Beuning-Pfaue, W., Holzapfel, W. and Betsche, T. (2005). Nutritional value of African yambean (*Sphenostylis stenocarpa* L): Improvement by Lactic acid fermentation. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 85(6): 963-970.

Bergthaler, W., Kesting, H.I., Velasco, I. and Gruneberg, W.J. (2001). Andean Yambean (*Pachyrhizus ahipa*) tubers, a new source of legume starch. Proceedings of the 4th European Conference in Grain Legumes, Cracow, Poland, 8-9 July, 2001.

Brun-Bellut, J., Lindberg, J.E. and Hadjipanayotou, M. (1991). Protein nutrition and requirement of adult dairy goats In: Goat Nutrition. Morand-Fehr (ed) EAAP Publication No. 46.Pp.82-93.

Crampton, E.W. and Harris, L.E (1969). *Applied Animal Nutrition: The use of feedstuffs in the formulation of livestock rations*. W.H. Freeman and Company. San Fransisco, U.S.A., Pp. 753.

Devendra, C. and Mcieroy, G.B. (1982). *Goat and Sheep Production in the Tropics*. W.J.A. Pange Pub., Longman, London and New York.

Duncan, D.B. (1955). Multiple Range and Multiple F-Tests. *Biometrics*, 11:1-42

European Association of Grain Legume Research (AEP) Paris, Pp 204-205.

Continental J. Agricultural Science

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Ezueh, M.I. (1984). African yambean as a crop in Nigeria. *World Crops*, 36(6): 199-200

FAO (1991). Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations: Livestock and Livestock Products. *Quarterly Bulletin of Statistics*, 4(3): 39, FAO. Rome, Italy.

Gruneberg, W.J., Goffman, F.D. and Velasco L. (1999). Characterization of yambean seeds as potential sources of high palmitic acid-oil. *JAOCs* 76:1309-1312

Hadjipanayiotou, M., Brun-Bellut, J. and Lindberg, J.A. (1991). Protein nutrition and requirements of growing goats. In: *Goat. Nutrition* Morand-Fehr.P. (ed). EAAP Publication No 46. Pudoc, Wageningen, The Netherlands. Pp 94-403.

Hernandez-Infante, M.A., Montalvo, S.I. and Tene, E. (1998). Impact of microwave heating on hemagglutinins, trypsin inhibitors and protein quality of selected legume seeds. *Plants Foods. Hum. Nutr.*, 52 (3): 199-208.

Ibeawuchi, J.A., Danjuma, A. and Oguntona, T. (1993). The value of dried poultry waste as a protein supplement for growing Bornu White goats. *Disc and Innov.*, 5(1): 63-68.

Ikhatua, U.H and Adu, I.F. (1984). A comparative evaluation of the utilization of groundnut haulms and *Digitaria smutsi* hay by Red Sokoto goats. *Anim. Prod. Res.*, 4(2): 145-152

Janardhanan, F., Gurumoothi, P. and Pugalenthil, M. (2003). Nutritional potential of five accessions of a South Indian tribal pulse, *Macuna pruriens var utilis*. *Tropical and Subtropical Agroecosystems*, 1 (2): 141-152.

Klu, G.Y.P., Amoatey, H.M., Bansa, D. and Kumaga, F.K. (2001). Cultivation and use African yambean (*Sphenostylis stenocarpa*) in the Volta Region of Ghana. *The Journal of Food Technology in Africa*. Vol 6. Pp. 74-77.

Leng, R.A. (1993). Practical technologies to optimize feed resource utilization in reference to the needs of animal agriculture in developing countries. In: Mack, S.D. (ed). *Strategies for Sustainable Animal Agriculture in Developing Countries*. FAO Production and Health Paper No. 107, Rome. Italy, FAO, Pp. 107-120.

Continental J. Agricultural Science

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ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Likukuyu, B., Sikumba, G., Kihara, J. and Bekunda, M. (2016). Intensification of small holder Livestock Production through utilization of Crop residues for livestock feed in Tanzania Tropentag, Vienna, Auistria, P. 158.

Matenga, V.R., Ngongoni, N.T., Titterton, M. and Maasdorp, B. V. (2003).Mucuna seed as a feed ingredient for small ruminants and effect of ensiling on its nutritive value. *Tropical and Sub tropical Agroecosystem*,1:97-105.

Mba, A.U., Egbuiwe, C.P. and Oyenuga. E.A. (1975). Nitrogen balance studies with Red Sokoto (Maradi) goats for the minimum protein requirements. *East African Agric. and Forestry Journal*, 40:285-291.

McDonald, P., Edwards, R.A., Greenhalgh, J.F.D. and Morgan, C.A. (1995). *Animal Nutrition* 5th Edition, Longman Publishers, Edinburgh, U K. P. 607.

Nuru, S. (1985). Trends in small ruminant production in Nigeria. In: *Small Ruminant Production in Nigeria*. I.F., Osinowow, O.A., Taiwo, B.B.A. and Alhassa, W.S. (eds). *Proceedings of the National Conference on Small Ruminant Production, Zaria, Nigeria*. 6-10th Oct. 1985 Pp. 35-51.

Obi, I.U. (1991). Statistical methods of detecting difference between treatment means. SWAPP Press. Nig. Ltd. Enugu, Nigeria, Pp. 45.

Onwuka, C.F.I., Akinsoyinu, A.O. and Mba A.U. (1985). Protein and energy requirements of West African Dwarf goats fed varying levels of browse (cassava) leaves and cassava peels. *Small Ruminant Production in Nigeria*, P. 281.

Oshodi, A.A., Ipinmoroti, K.O. and Adeyeye, E.I. (1997). Functional properties of some varieties of African yambean (*Sphenostylis stenocarpa*) Flour-111. *Int. J. Food Sci. Nutr.* 48 (4): 243-250.

Preston, T.R. (1986). Better utilization of crop residue and by-products in animal feeding. Research guidelines. 2.A practical manual for research workers. *FAO Animal Prod. and Health Paper* 50/2, Pp. 23-24.

Reeve, S. (2017). Cashing in on Cassava. SPORE-N:1841 March-May 2017, 8-9.

Continental J. Agricultural Science

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Rishkowsky, B.A., Ates, S., Wamatu, J., EL. Dine Hilali, M., Abbeddou, S. and Nurbekov, A. (2016) in Drylands for enhanced livestock productivity and efficient resource use. Tropentag, 2016, Vienna, Austria, P. 151.

Santos, A.C.O., Cavalcanti, M.S.M. and Coello, L.C.B.B. (1996). Chemical composition and nutritional potential of yambean seeds. *Plants Foods For Human Nutrition* 49: 36-41.

Sauvant., D. and Morand-Fehr, P. and Giger-Reverdins, S. (1991). Dry matter of adult Goats. In: Goat Nutrition Morand-Fehr, P. (Ed), EAAP. Publication No. 46 pudoc. Wageningen. The Netherlands pp. 25-36.

Smith, O.B., Idowu, A.O., Asaolu, V.O. and Odunlanu, M.O. (1988). Comparative rumen degradability of forages, browses, crop residue and by-products. In: African Small Ruminant Research and Development in Africa. R.T.Wilson and M.Azeb. ILCA, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. Pp 204-20a8.

SPSS (2006). Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). SPSS Inc. 15.0 Evaluation Version for Windows.

Swanson, K.C., Calton, J.C., Redmer, D.A., Burke, V.E and Reynolds, L.P. (2000). Influence of undegraded protein on intake., digestion, serum hormones, metabolites and nitrogen balance in sheep. *Small Rum. Res.*, 35: 225-233.

Ukachukwu, S.N. and Obioha, F.C. (2000). Effect of time duration of thermal treatments on the nutritive value of *Mucuna cochinchinensis*. *Global Journal of Pure and Appl. Sciences*, 6(1): 11-15.

Ukpabi, U.H. (2007). Evaluation of Mucuna Seed meal based diets for goat production in South-eastern Nigeria. Ph.D. Thesis. MOUNAU, Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria.

Enhancing Small Scale Forest Users Entrepreneurship

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Abstract

This paper examines the roles of forestry and forest products in income generating activities especially in the face of globalization and ever increasing changes in forest ecosystem. This paper, however, highlight some measures that will enhance the entrepreneurship of forest users.

Keywords: Entrepreneurs, income generating, forest products, wood

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Introduction

Forestry and forest products form a significant item of economic activities bringing substantial amount of money to rural communities and National economy. The structure of forestry, is indicative of its specialized nature as an economic activity in which man produces wood and other forest products, it has the potential of stimulating the growth and development of entrepreneurs (Olayide *et al.*, 1975). According to Olayide *et al.*, (1975) forestry is define as the management of forest for the continuous production of goods and services in responds to the need for an ultimate satisfaction of consumer's desires.

Forest Enterprises

The scope of forest enterprises in the small scale forest sector is conditioned predominantly by the demand for forest products. The diverse small scale forest enterprises include among others - Logging, Hunting, Gathering, Harvesting and Farming, Worth of mentioning are other allied economic activities such as wood

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industries, furniture making Grafting which provide employment opportunities and generate income for the unskilled, semi-skilled and skilled forest dwellers.

Many hundreds of millions of people across the developing world trade in diverse range of timber and Non-timber forest products, every day and which are marketed primarily in local and regional domestic market (Schenker *et al.*, 2004; Osalusi *et al.*, 2011).

In many sector, small scale enterprises have long dominated economic activity, that they are faced with new challenges in the context of globalization facilitating forest entrepreneurship demand special efforts, especially if consideration is given to the many changes which forest ecosystem is currently going through worldwide. Therefore the future of small scale forest enterprises will depend on large part on the ability of the sector to adopt to change.

There is no doubting that, the Nigerian forest based enterprises operate under an atmosphere of uncertainty, thus affecting the performance of their economic role. Adeyoju (1970) opined that the effective performance of their role is impeded by a number of factors such as:-

1. The ineffectual role of entrepreneurs in many developing countries.
2. The poor development of organizational frame work for the efficient mobilization of production.
3. Inadequate capital supply for the production and distribution aspect of the forestry economy.
4. The continuous lack of technical know how and the apparent slowness of the adoption of innovation in production and distribution of forestry products.

The greatest challenge to small scale forest based entrepreneurs; arise majorly in the search for cost - effective strategies, couple with the issue of producing enough products in a context of rapidly rising urbanization, desertification and deforestation. Despite many favourable attributes, the average small scale forest based enterprise have, the enterprise still often struggle for survival in a hostile environment.

Motivational Strategies for Enhancement

The painted background of instability in the small scale forest enterprise has haunted the forest users with serious and adverse consequences on their development process. From the foregoing, it is obvious that we have a great challenge at hand which needs immediate attention by all stakeholders. One would therefore, make the following recommendations;

Recommendations

1. The small scale forest based entrepreneur should be protected from competition from large scale enterprises.
2. There should be an improvement in access to credit facilities to start and sustain their business. An efficient credit system will allow for the fulfillment of forestry role of economic activity.
3. There should be an improvement in access to technology in terms of suitable tools and equipment.
4. There should be promotion of association, cluster and cooperatives to enable small scale benefits from scale economics, in procurement of inputs, transport and promotion of products and research. According to Macqueen *et al.* (2006): the small scale entrepreneurs in the forest sector do often sense a need to connect with one another. They work together to strengthen their political voice and their bargaining power in the market. He stressed further that association help small enterprise adapt to new market opportunities and rescue their transaction cost. Elsewhere in the literature, Kazoora *et al.* (2006) revealed that, in Uganda alone, there are estimated 2000 to 3000 forest based association.
5. Education / Training will ensure the full realization of economic empowerment and strengthened their management skill. Lack of education / training perpetuate dependency, ignorance and poverty.
6. Enterprise should be linked up with secured and larger markets.
7. Lack and shortage of raw material due to seasonality, wasteful processing, poor distribution and restriction by government regulation should be eliminated.

Accordingly to White *et al.* (2007), small forest enterprises should exist legally and be granted secure tenure and access to forest resources and be taxes fairly.

8. Network of road should be developed for evacuation of products.
9. Afforestation should be encouraged by introducing the old rule of fell one plant one.
10. Encourage the forest users on preservation of biodiversity because all over the world, forest resources are increasingly scarce in particular preferred species, qualities and size. This is a growing constraint in continued activity.
11. Forest entrepreneur should be helped to identify additional products that can also contribute to a higher level of income thus allowing for saving and investment in long term forest resource development.
12. Special contribution should be given to women folks in the forest based small scale enterprises.
13. Energy and electricity should be improved, mostly to improve the comfort of work.
14. There should be provision of information and other adversary services.
15. Government policy should be reformed on forest trade for small scale enterprises because, until recently the policy had favoured large and organized forest trade thus neglecting small scale enterprises besides the poor and small scale forest enterprises should have representation in policy and decision making process

Conclusion

In summary, the potential of the forest for income generation cannot be over emphasized, but when damage is done through lack of concern for sustainability of the forest environment, then the economic activity and roles of the forest becomes low and fully aborted, but hope may be raised when necessary, measure are taken

References

- Adeyoju, S. K. (1970): "A survey of the Nigerian Timber Economy" Bulletin of Rural Economics and sociology. Vol. 5 No 1.1970.
- Kazooru C, *et al.* (2006): Forest based association as drivers for sustainable Development in Uganda, London, UK Sustainable Development Centre (SDC) and IIED.
- Macqueen, D. J. Bose 5, Bukula 5, Kazooru C., Ousman, S., Porro, N. and Weyerhaeuser, H. (2006): Working together "Forest linked small and medium enterprises associations and collective action Gate keeper series No 125 London, UK IIED
- Olayide S. A., Ogunfowora, O., Essang, S.M. and Idachaba, F. S. (1975): Element of Rural Economics Ibadan. University Press Publishing House University of Ibadan, Ibadan.
- Osalusi, C.S., Usman, J.M. and Pitan, O.O. (2011): Profitability of Non-Timber forest products in Rain forest Area of Ondo State Nigeria *J. Forestry Research and Management* Vol 8. Pg 27 - 33.
- Schanker A., *et al.* (2004): livelihood gains and ecological costs of NTFP dependence: - assessing the role of dependence, ecological knowledge and manhet structure in three contesting human and ecological settings in South India Germany.
- White, A., Kozak R. and Liddle, M. (2007): The large and growing role of SMFE paper presented at a side event of the 7th session of United Nation Forum of Forest (UNFF). Small forest enterprises: - Drivers of Sustainable Development New York USA 23rd April.

Environmental Implication of Livestock Development

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Abstract

This paper attempts to elucidate the diverse environmental implications of livestock development. This paper aimed at examining and highlighting the types of livestock management system to bring out the environmental implications; with a view to fully understand the complexity of each system.

Keywords: *environmental implications, agriculture, livestock, pastoralist, farmers*

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Introduction

In the process of raising the general standard of living of its people various governments of developing and developed nation have pursued policies on Agriculture, Industrialization, Transportation and on exploitation of national resources for a better and more meaningful life without being mindful of the need to strike a healthy balance between our development pursuit and a quality environment; because forever development and no matter the how small development is, there is a corresponding environmental degradation or changes in what the environment use to be (FAO, 1974).

Amongst, this developmental effort is the developing of livestock industry- an integral part of Agriculture, which in an integrated economic activity upon which over several millions of farmers and pastoralist derives their livelihood. The development aims at ensuring efficient production, raising productivity, promoting animal and human health and ensuring adequate and equitable return to producers. The industry has a significant role in the socio-economic development of nation, as source of food of animal protein origin for animal and human consumption, provider of manure,

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cultivation of farm land, serve an insurance against crop failure and use as a measure of social status amongst the traditional livestock rearers.

The main objective of this paper is to review the sources of environmental degradation and problems due to the development of livestock sub-sector in Agriculture.

Livestock Products and It's by Products

The term livestock refers to animal kept on farms and other biting insect and creature so, on broad economic sense, livestock includes domesticated and wild animal that are used for human consumption. The main agricultural animals of the world are, cattle, sheep, pig, and goat, buffalo, horse, ass and mule of course including poultry. These agricultural animal could in turn be grouped as ruminant and non-ruminant. Other animals that are of considerably important in livestock development, but not common as human food or have more or less economic significance are Cat, Dog, Monkey etc which are generally refers to as "Pet".

However, livestock industry also involved production of primary products and or by products such as meat (poultry, beef, pork, mutton), milk eggs, hides and skins for leather industry, draftpower and transportation, dung for manure and fuel, and offals and bones for the industries, others include production of milk products, like curd, cheese, yoghurt, butter and ghee, chhena and khoa (made in Asia), condense milk, dried milk and ice-cream. In addition to these are hair, Wool, Hooves, Horns, blood, Gases, heat, methane and urine.

System of Livestock Management

The environment in which livestock is introduced are physical and human environment. The physical environment includes the land (soil), atmosphere, and others. Living and non-living things occurring in space.

Livestock industry occurs under different management systems and the effect of these various system on the environment would be highlighted in this section. The systems of livestock management are (a) Extensive management system (b) Intensive management system (c) Semi-intensive management system, this falls in between the other two.

Extensive Management System

This system is well practiced and almost dominated by the traditional Nomadic cattle rearers in most Africa countries such as the West, North east, East Africa, than the

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Western Asia. The major features of this system is that animals are led to moving around in search of grazing and water and or left on their own to roam about the bush and street in search of pasture or scavenging for food materials.

In the wake of this migration, the animal's transverse many lands leading to varying results and consequences such as the destruction of crops and pollution of drinking water. This condition often leads to serious conflict between pastoral nomads and sedentary farmers, as it was evidenced in Kano and Plateau State (Awe and Doma Local Governments).

In addition to this, the movement of cattle under this system enhances the spread of many zoonotic diseases, i.e. the diseases that are infectious and naturally transmitted between Animal and man, and Animal to Animal. Zoonoses constitute an important component of the whole public health field and are one of the most important areas of veterinary public health activities. Among the zoonosis recognized today are Anthrax, Brucellosis, Tuberculosis, Rabies and Several of the more arthropod borne viral infection such as Tick borne relapsing fever (WHO, 1974).

The following are some of the Zoonotic diseases.

Anthrax

This is also called wool sorte disease for the germs used to be hidden in wools, hides and skins. In man this disease can show as localized postules. People at risk include livestock farmers, people working in abattoirs and health personnel including laboratory staff.

Brucellosis

Brucellosis is a disease of cattle, goat and sheep caused by a causative agent called Bovine melitensis which is highly virulent for man. WHO (1974) gave a stock ton of estimation of about 350 million U S dollars annually and that substantial members of human cases of incapacitating illness had been reported in America alone.

In fact, most of the infectious of man that have been discovered in the last 20 years are shared with lowers animals and a number of diseases previously thought to be limited to man have been found to be Zoonoses (WHO, 1974).

The method (Mode of infection) by which Human beings can contact these diseases are usually by unknowingly eating (ingesting) the causative germ (Bacteria or Virus) either

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by eating with dirty hands or breathing in the germs (aerosol droplet method) e.g. tuberculosis.

Moreover, the traditional livestock rearers often goes about with their bows and arrows for hunting purposes and such hunting activities also are particularly responsible for the destruction of wild animals that are in fact a part of balance of Nature. Cattle utilize the plant that is desirable to the recreationist from an aesthetic point of view. Littering of better camp site, in their transient nature along the stream is an unacceptable source of contamination couple with the smell and offensive nature of their droppings.

Roaming of livestock in the street has often caused destruction of flowers, bed in many homes, destruction of valuable properties especially in market areas, where loosed animals are often seen entering into stalls to eat traders' good and foodstuff. In addition, goats, sheep and cattle are often seen crossing roads at random and arbitrary and as such they often caused accidents on the roads claiming lives.

Though, the extensive range land grazing system provides the cheapest source of feed for livestock, but the dangers is that with the increasing pressure from other competitive land use, the grazing land diminishes and this gives rise to over-concentration of livestock on land with the attendant problem of trampling, leaf defoliation and of course, overgrazing.

Grazing is complex system that involves soils, plants and animals interacting with factors to govern their behaviour. In such a system the physical factors, plant and animals function as a unit and any changes in one factor, such as caused by grazing or drought changes the whole complex (Noy - Mein, 1975). With over-grazing, undesirable effect such as disappearance of forage occur as this lead to exposition of soil to erosion, reducing soil productivity and consequently changes the original plant community. The evidence of this effects can be observed in Northern part of Nigeria especially in Sokoto, Kano and Borno where overgrazing has resulted in the gradual changes of the original plants to low value forage plant such as *Cassia tora*, *Waltheris americana*, *Acanthospermum hispidum* (Kallah, 1982).

Intensive System

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The livestock producer of the past had operated largely and almost independently of other segments of the population because there was little population pressure, consequently, he was far from urban centres, but the position has changed drastically as

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a result of the rapid population increase. The inordinate rapid growth in population has proportionately increased the demand for open space and as well as a voice in how this space might affect their lives, therefore considering this and the animal protein needs vis-a-vis poor productivity from extensive management system, the traditional system of livestock production has to give way to intensive system of production in order to meet the ever increasing demand for animal protein.

The notably feature of the intensive system is the fixed building, where the livestock are kept in confinement with the provision of all essential infrastructure like water supply, pasture development, road, fencing, high plane of nutrition etc. However, high intensity livestock production satisfies the need to improve the efficiency of livestock management and to exploit the genetically constituents of livestock through application of technology in the principle of livestock nutrition and disease control. But rather than removing the environmental impact, it has increased the extent of it. It is under this system of livestock production that the technological innovation feedlot operation (Ranching) and poultry houses are classified.

The changes to confinement of livestock have magnified deforestation and production of animal waste such as excreta. The disposal of wastes from the system has developed into a major problem in recent years particularly, in the developed nations of the world where livestock production is done on a very large scale. Though excreta is used as manure, but however, in some instances the area of land available may be inadequate and climatic and topographical feature may restrict the amount of excreta that can be applied, thus a varying amount of it is lost from the system as run-off, when it rains, into the surface and underground water (Vukina, 2001).

For instance, the run-off feedlot and chicken dropping has been reported to contain Managanese (Mn) and Zinc (Zn) which can locally contaminate surface water and shallow under ground water. Other wastes (organic) that constitute additional resources within land economy in the system are silage liquor that may seep away during processing and conservation of herbage. Though the actual wastes handle depends upon the stock variation, feed variations, drinking water system, cleaning and budding methods.

In another study, an increase in Nitrogen (N₂) from 2mg/litre to 15mg/litre has been reported in a run-off as it flowed under a barn yard. Chicken manure has also been reported to be the sources of organisms causing human respiratory diseases caused by

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fungus *Histoplasma capsulatum*, the pathogen is air borne from dry dropping chicken manure. The most common of local environmental impact which often may be regarded as small nuisance but, which can in some circumstances causes considerable distress are (i) Flies (ii) Odour (iii) Noise (iv) Effluent - such as slurry which however, could be used as fertilizer and at the same time serve as disease and parasites transmitter . Vukina (2001) also reported that, the increase in fly population in California is ascribed to livestock concentrations that have moved nearer the cities and also to residential expansion towards the farm with their new livestock practices.

A report from the independent commission on international humanitarian issues has it that 38% of deforestation in Brazil between 1966 and 1975 was due to ranching. In another, reports, it was said that almost three quarter Brazil cleared forest is used for cattle ranching and that an area of 2 million hectares is cleared each year for the purpose of supplying cheap meat (Beef) for export to North America. This view is equally supported by (Williamson and Pyne, 1978).

Intensive system of livestock involves the use of drugs and chemicals in food production and such drugs has associated problem of drug residue especially with copper and arsenic containing drugs. This then bring about the issue of food hygiene in respect of the dairy industry, abattoir and livestock feed mill - developed as subsidiary industries from intensive system of diversity production. Food hygiene is concerned with the conditions and method of production, processing, storage and distribution and aims at ensuring safe and wholesome products fit for human consumption. Food borne pathogen such as *Vibrio parchaem* has been recognized.

Dairy Industry

The major product from dairy industry is milk and milk products that are consumable. Other products that can be classified as waste includes waste water from the cleansing of the milking machine and parlour, corn, and boxes that may constitute nuisance to the environment, if, they are not properly disposed or discharged to avoid draining into soil by percolation and seepage into groundwater. Human beings, however, could be infected by Tuberculosis through milk, especially raw milk if taken. The waste water from Dairy industry measure as oxygen consumption (BOD) has been reported to be three to four times more polluted than household wastes water.

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Abattoir

Slaughter house by products arising from the slaughtering of livestock includes Blood, Bones, Horns and Hoofs and water from the cleansing of the slaughtered animal and slaughter house floor. Though quite a number of these products have now been put into productive use, however, the only danger there is that, of disposal of them adequately because, they can equally constitute nuisance and eye sore in the environment.

Feed Mill Plants

These are allied industries developed from intensive system of livestock production. These plants produce concentrated feed for animal production. Some of the pollutants from the industry may include dust and fumes, effluent discharge, suspended solid, and thermal pollution.

Environmental Management in Livestock Industry

Livestock production base consists of renewable resources that must be sustained against degradation and such resource includes range land, soil, water, of course human and livestock generation sources. However, efforts have been geared up in most Countries of the world towards the establishments of grazing reserves as a response to the deleterious effects of traditional system of livestock production. In some of these grazing reserves, pasture were developed and partition into paddocks so that livestock can graze on rotational basis among there paddocks, to prevent overgrazing which might result into soil erosion or extinction of plant species. This measure however, many reduce the spread of transmission of diseases from animal to animal and from animal to man.

Yet there is no single method generally satisfactory for the treatment of the animal manure originating in confinement livestock operation. Methods that have, however, been employed in most cases include field spreading as manure, composting, lagooning, incineration and possibly the dehydration of the excreta. As a matter of fact, it is pertinent to say here that animals droppings has been incorporated on a lower level into poultry feeding as a source of protein feed and biogas production.

Conclusion and Recommendation

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The environmental impact of extensive, intensive and livestock base industry have hitherto not been fully appreciated in most developing countries especially in Nigeria. Hence, the information which is available in this topic is rather scarce. Therefore, there

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should be conscious efforts towards creating awareness in area of environmental pollution or implication of livestock production.

Intensive animal production and industrial food processing have given rise to problems of waste disposal, pollution of water, air, and soil on which man survival on earth depends. Therefore, efforts should be geared up towards the reduction or elimination of these various environmental hazards.

Finally,

1. A comprehensive animal and human health care delivery service should be established.
2. More grazing reserves land should be established with adequate provision of infrastructure for the existence ones.
3. Veterinarians should be adequately encouraged and equipped because; they play a key role in the field of maintaining sanitary hygiene at slaughter houses, farm houses and associated industries.
4. There should be strict enforcement of the existing legislation regarding all matters of Animal and Human Health.

References

- Charles W. Abdalla and Jennnifer L. Lawton (2006): Environmental issues in Animal Agriculture 21 (3) in the magazine if food, farm and resource issue.
- FAO (1974): Environment and Development 13th FAO Regional Conference for Latin America, Panama City, Panama pg. 1-11.
- Kallah M.S (1982): Grassland Management in Nigeria In proceeding of National conference on Beef production Kaduna, Nigeria July 27 - 30

Noy - Mein, I. (1975): Stability of grazing system an application of predator-preygrapho. *Journal of Ecology* 63, 459 - 491

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Adedeji (2019) 13 (1): 24 - 32

WHO (1974): Chronicle report of veterinary public health - A reviews of the WHO programme 28, 103 - 112 and 108 -181

Vukina, T. (2001): The relationship between contracting and line stock waste pollution. White paper National centre for manure and Animal waste management. Raleigh, NC

Williamson G. and Payne W.J.A (1978) An introduction to Animal Husbandry in the tropical 3rd Edition BLRS/Longman